

**ILMIY VA
INNOVATSION
TERAPIYA**

**SCIENTIFIC >>> >>>
AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY**

МИНИСТЕРСТВО ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ
РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН

SCIENTIFIC AND INNOVATIVE
THERAPY

ИЛМИЙ ВА ИННОВАЦИОН
ТЕРАПИЯ

НАУЧНАЯ И ИННОВАЦИОННАЯ
ТЕРАПИЯ

Научный журнал по научной и инновационной терапии
основано в 2022 году

Бухарским государственным медицинским институтом
имени Абу Али ибн Сино
выходит один раз в 2 месяца

Главный редактор – Ш.Ж. ТЕШАЕВ

Редакционная коллегия:

*Н.Ш. Ахмедова (зам. главного редактора),
Ш.А. Наимова (ответственный секретарь),
Г.Ж. Жарилкасинова, Н.А. Нуралиев, К.Ж. Болтаев,
Ф.Э. Нурбаев, С.М. Бахрамов, А.Г. Гадаев,
А.Ш. Иноятлов, Р.Б. Абдуллаев*

*Учредитель Бухарский государственный
медицинский институт имени Абу Али ибн Сино*

2024, № 3

ISSN
2181-418X

Адрес редакции:

Республика Узбекистан, 200100,
г. Бухара, ул. А. Гиждувани, 23.

Телефон:

(99865) 223-00-50

Факс

(99866) 223-00-50

Сайт

<https://ivit.uz/>

e-mail

shnaimova5@gmail.com

О журнале

Журнал зарегистрирован
в Управлении печати и информации
Бухарской области
№ 1640 от 28.05.2022 г.

Подписано в печать 20.11.2023.

Формат 60×84 1/8

Усл. П.л. 41,39

Заказ 104

Тираж 50 экз.

Отпечатано в типографии Шарк

140151, г. Бухары,

ул. Амира Темура, 18

Редакционный совет:

Anand Ahuja	(Индия)
Nordin Simbak	(Малайзия)
Tetsuo Sasano	(Япония)
Ali O'zdemir	(Туркия)
Есаян А.М.	(Россия)
Арипова Т.У.	(Узбекистан)
Ахмедов Р.М.	(Узбекистан)
Амонов М.К.	(Узбекистан)
Бадритдинова М.Н.	(Узбекистан)
Бобоев К.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Давлатов С.С.	(Узбекистан)
Дустова Н.К.	(Узбекистан)
Курманова Г.М.	(Казахстан)
Қаюмов А.А.	(Узбекистан)
Мавлянов З.И.	(Узбекистан)
Набиева Д.А.	(Узбекистан)
Неъматов Ж.М.	(Узбекистан)
Рахматова Д.И.	(Узбекистан)
Саноева М.Ж.	(Узбекистан)
Сулаймонова Г.Т.	(Узбекистан)
Тўракулов Р.И.	(Узбекистан)
Шодикулова Г.З.	(Узбекистан)
Эгамова С.Қ.	(Узбекистан)
Юлдашева Д.Х.	(Узбекистан)
Убайдуллаева З.И.	(Узбекистан)

Predictors of the development of cardiorenal syndrome in patients with chronic kidney disease

Tukhtaev D.A.

Bukhara State Medical Institute, Uzbekistan, Bukhara

Resume. Cardiorenal relationships are one of the pressing problems of today's medicine. It is especially important to determine the degree of primary injury of these two pathologies. This article presents the results of a retrospective examination in which 4 types of cardiorenal syndrome are spread and factors that cause comorbidity are analyzed for evaluation purposes. The results obtained showed that the frequency of occurrence of Vascular Pathology in SBKS depends on the clinical level and age aspect of the disease.

Key words: Comorbidity, cardiorenal syndrome, chronic heart disease

Предикторы развития кардиоренального синдрома у больных хронической болезнью почек

Тухтаев Д.А.

Бухарский государственный медицинский институт, Узбекистан, Бухара

Резюме. Кардиоренальные отношения-одна из актуальных проблем современной медицины. Особенно важным считается определение степени первичного поражения этих двух патологий. В этой статье представлены результаты ретроспективного исследования, в котором анализируется Распространенность кардиоренального синдрома 4 типа и факторы, вызывающие коморбидность, с целью оценки. Полученные результаты показали, что частота встреч сосудистой патологии в случае СБК зависит от клинической степени заболевания и возраста.

Ключевые слова: Коморбидность, кардиоренальный синдром, хронические сердечные заболевания

Сурункали буйрак касаллигида кардиоренал синдром ривожланишининг предикторлари

Tuxtayev D.A.

Buxoro davlat tibbiyot instituti, O'zbekiston, Buxoro

Rezyume. Kardiorenal munosabatlar bugungi kun tibbiyotining dolzarb muammolaridan biridir. Ayniqsa bu ikki patologiyaning birlamchi shikastlanish darajasini aniqlash juda muhim sanaladi. Ushbu maqolada kardiorenal sindromning 4 tipi tarqalganligi va komorbidlik holatini keltirib chiqaruvchi omillar baholash maqsadida tahlil qilingan retrospektiv tekshirish natijalari keltirilgan. Olingan natijalar SBK larida qon tomir patologiyasi uchrash chastotasi kasallik klinik darajasi va yosh jihatiga bog'liqligini ko'rsatdi.

Kalit so'zlar: Komorbidlik, kardiorenal sindrom, surunkali yurak kasalliklari

Comorbidity is one of the relevant and most important clinical problems found in the practice of doctors of all specialties, since in the diagnosis and treatment of patients with joint pathology, specialties from the doctor require an intermediate preparation and approach.

There is no single approach to signifying the definition and essence of comorbidity. While some authors interpret the combination of two or more diseases in patients that are pathogenetically related to each other as comorbidity, others believe that comorbidity means that the patient has two or more diseases that differ in etiology, pathogenesis and methods of treatment.

Data on the prevalence of comorbid diseases also differ slightly from each other, and this depends on a number of circumstances, including whether the patient is being treated in the primary system or in specialized hospitals, gender, age, predisposition to medical examinations, and a number of other factors. In all cases, however, comorbidity increases as the patient ages [1,7,8].

Comorbidity incidence reaches 69% at age 18-44, 93% at age 45-64, and 98% at age over 65 [2.3.5].

In most studies, it has been noted that high comorbidity decreases quality of life, leading to impaired social adaptation and an increase in mortality [6,9]. The high incidence and increasing incidence of comorbidity is indicative of the need to study this problem for Uzbekistan, among many countries [4].

Concomitant heart and kidney damage is common among the population and is often attributed to increased mortality, risk of complications and disability, increased complexity of treatment and cost of treatment. In addition, today there are good reasons to discuss the totality of pathogenesis, the development factors of chronic kidney disease and chronic heart disease, the need for separate approaches to their joint treatment.

Heart and kidney problems are of double importance, in one of which pathophysiological disorder can lead to dysfunction of another, and this condition is being used with the concept of "cardiorenal syndrome" (KRS). [1, 2].

KRS means that at some point the patient has heart and kidney failure or dysfunction, the patient has primary renal pathology, the effect of which is the development of heart failure, or vice versa, cardiac pathology is primary, and heart failure has been observed to develop kidney damage and kidney failure (E.V. Reznik).

C. According to the classification proposed by Ronco (2008), there are five types of cardiorenal syndrome. These are: acute cardiorenal Syndrome – Type 1; chronic cardiorenal syndrome - type 2; acute renocardial Syndrome-Type 3;

chronic renocardial Syndrome-Type 4 and secondary cardiorenal syndrome-type 5.

In the last decade after the development of the concept of chronic kidney diseases, doctors operating in different specialties of Medicine in research conducted on a global scale began to see the results of comprehensive careful approaches to the problems of the course, or development of SBK in combination with other diseases.

In particular, it is observed that one of the chronic disorders of kidney and heart function leads to the formation of pathogenetics, sometimes joint development, complications and exacerbation of disability.

The purpose of our research work is to retrospectively study the incidence rate, risk factors, pathogenic and clinical characteristics of KRS Type 4.

Research material and methods. As a research material, in 2015 and 2022, 350 disease histories of inpatient treated patients were studied and analyzed in the terpia, cardiology and Nephrology Department of the Bukhara regional Multidisciplinary Medical Center.

In the study of the history of the disease, on the basis of the KRS classification, an analysis of indications of ECG, EXOKG, laboratory markers (creatinine, BKFT, lipid fractions) was evaluated in order to determine the types of primary occurrence of cardiac yoke renal pathology in patients ' Anamnesis, chronic kidney disease (SBK) and cardiac dysfunction.

Research results and discussion. Based on the creatinine residue in laboratory analyzes in the history of the analyzed 350 diseases, filtration of kidney balls using the CKD-EPI formula was calculated, and SBK levels were diagnosed in patients. Analysis in the history of the disease revealed different levels of SBK in 137 patients.

Of the patients studied in the history of the disease, 76 made up 55.4% of men and 61 (44.6%) of women. The average age of patients was 48 ± 1.7 . When SBK-causing risk factors were identified from the analyzed disease histories, 42.4% (59) patients were diagnosed with hypertension, 28.6 % (39) had YuIK, stenocardia, and 39.9% (55) had sue. When SBK levels were identified, nephropathies were found in SBK 1 levels 11 (8%), SBK 2 levels 43 (31.4%), 37 (27%) SBK 3 a and 46 (33.6%) levels 3B.

Patients with SBK also showed an increase in cardiac symptom incidence as the rate of development of nephropathy increases when the incidence of diseases and symptoms associated with cardiovascular activity observed in the formation of cardiorenal syndrome was analyzed, i.e. there was a positive proportional relationship between the rate of renal dysfunction and the rate of cardiac symptom occurrence.

When we analyzed the incidence rate of cardiorenal Syndrome Type 4 depending on age and gender aspect, the following results were obtained. The age division group was based on the WHO classification in 2017. In this, the ages of 18-44 were 42 (30.6%), the ages of 45-59 (middle age) were 82 (59.8%) and the ages of 60-74 (old age) were 13, making up 9.5%. 73.8% of 42 patients aged 18-44 were diagnosed with hypertension, 26.4% with YuIK (stenocardial), 4.4% with atherosclerosis, 5.2% with arrhythmia, and 3.7% with Sue. In the middle age, however, hypertension was diagnosed in 68.3% of cases, arrhythmia in 11.6%, YuIK in 28.7%, sue in 31.4%, and 4 (2.9%) patients were diagnosed with acute cerebral circulation disorder in their Anamnesis.

There is a correlation between age and cardiorenal syndrome in the form of positive proportional growth, as can be seen from the analyzes. In 38.1% of patients, Cardiological pathologies in cardiorenal syndrome were observed to occur in 2 or more comorbidities.

When analyzed gender-wise, no major differences were found between the incidence of cardiorenal syndrome among men and women.

Conclusion. It can be said that in patients with chronic kidney disease, factors that assess brak vascular activity are common, the incidence of which depends on the severity and age aspect of SBK.

The most common comorbid conditions include hypertension (42.2%) and Sue (38%), which at the same time increases comorbidity, complications of kidney dysfunction.

List of bibliography

1. Boltayev K. J., Akhmedova N. Sh. Characteristic phenomenon razvitiya polydeficitnix sostoyaniy pri starenii / / problem biologii I medicini. – 2020. - T. 1. - S. 24-26.
2. Alyavi A.L., Kamilova U.K., Rasulova Z.D. Diagnostics I lecheniye chronicheskoy serdechnoy nedostatochnosti. // Monograph. – 2016. - S.196
3. Belyalov F. I. Lecheniye vnutrennix bolezney v usloviyax komorbidnosti. // monogr. - 8-E izd.- Irkutsk: RIO IGIUVa, -2013.- S. 285.
4. Murkamilov I.T., Aytbayev K.A., Murkamilova J.A., Fomin V.V., Rayimjanov Z.R., Redjapova N.A., Yusupov F.A., Aydarov Z.A. Klinicheskoye znacheniye markyrovov pochechnoy dysfunctsii v stratifikatsii serdechno-sosudistogo riska. Eurasiysky Cardiologichesky Journal. 2018;(4):64-78. <https://doi.org/10.38109/2225-1685-2018-4-64-78>
5. Tuxtayev D.A. Modern view on the problems of cardiorenal syndrome. Art of Medicine. International Medical Scientific Journal 2.3 (2022).

6. Benetti E., Mastrocola R., Vitarelli G., et al. Empagliflozin Protects against Diet-Induced NLRP-3 Inflammasome Activation and Lipid Accumulation. // *J Pharmacol Exp Ther.* -2016; -№ 359 (1). - R.45-53.
7. Cruz D.N., Schmidt-Ott K.M., Vescovo G., et al. Pathophysiology of cardiorenal syndrome type 2 in stable chronic heart failure: work group statements from the eleventh consensus conference of the Acute Dialysis Quality Initiative (ADQI). // *Contributor Nephrol.* -2013. - R.182. - R.117–136.
8. Herzog C.A., Asinger R.W., Berger A.K. et al. Cardiovascular disease in chronic kidney disease. A clinical update from Kidney Disease: Improving Global Outcomes (KDIGO). // *Kidney Int.*- 2011.-№80. - R.572-586.
9. Tkachenko Ye.I., Borovkova N.Yu., Buyanova M.V anemia pri chronicheskoy serdechnoy nedostatochnosti: Vzgl'yad na pathogenesis i puti korrektsii. // *Cardiology Therapy* -2019. - №2 (157), - DOI:10.31550/1727-2378-2019-157-2-31-36.
10. Ashurovich T. D. Cardiorenal syndrome in patients with early stages of chronic heart failure // *Asian journal of pharmaceutical and biological research.* – 2023. – T. 12. – №. 2.